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Researcher Early Career

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MINIMUM VIABLE SKILLS PROFILE

Researcher Early Career Minimum Viable Skills Profile

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Disclaimer

This booklet is part of the **Skills4EOSC collection of Minimum Viable Skills Profiles (MVS)**, which outline key Open Science competencies for different professional roles. It presents a focused extract from the **Annex to Deliverable D2.6**, designed to support usability and communication. To explore the full list of profiles, visit the Skills4EOSC website (<https://www.skills4eosC.eu/resources/publications/mvs>) or consult the full Annex (<https://zenodo.org/records/15761916>).

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

CARE	Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics	MVS	Minimum Viable Skillset
CSCCE	Centre for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement	ORCC	Open Research Competencies Coalition
DMP	Data Management Plan	OS	Open Science
ELSI	Ethical, Legal and Social Issues	R&I	Research and Innovation
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud	RDA	Research Data Alliance
ETHRD IG	Education and Training on Handling of Research Data Interest Group (RDA)	RDM	Research Data Management
ICT	Information and Communication Technology	RI	Research Infrastructure
IT	Information Technology	RPO	Research Performing Organisation
JRC	Joint Research Centre	RSE	Research Software Engineer
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable	T4fs	Terms for FAIR skills

1. Introduction

Open Science mission for this role

Early Career Researchers for the purposes of this Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) include PhD students, postdoctoral researchers, and other researchers within 5 to 8 years of completion of their doctorate degree. The MVS addresses the competencies and skills needed by Researchers in the early stages of their research career as is related to Open OS.

A key principle of Open Science (OS) is that research is conducted openly and transparently leading to better science. **Researchers have a key role in the promotion of Open Science (OS) and its practice.** Not only do early career researchers contribute to the wider uptake of skills, building their own individual skills and organizational capacities, openness is at the core of the researchers role. They are an integral part of all production and dissemination of knowledge.

OS can be facilitated via data sharing, exploring and reusing data and, data publication, and making codes available, promoting open research through peer review, and reproducible research. By adopting OS approaches, **Researchers work to ensure that the benefits which openness brings**, such as the accessibility, reproducibility and transparency of research, are available to students, colleagues, and to society as a whole.

RESEARCHER - EARLY CAREER

ASSOCIATED FUNCTION TITLES:

- Occupations at levels R1 and R2 in the [European Framework for Research Careers](#), e.g. PhD students, Post-doctoral researchers
- Other researchers (working outside of academia and research councils)

ESSENTIAL SKILLS FOR THIS ROLE

- Good understanding of OS and its practices, in a discipline-specific context, particularly knowledgeable of policies, opportunities and practices of OS (e.g., open access, data storage and archival).
- Sound knowledge of the data life cycle and adequate capacity to implement FAIR principles using discipline-specific resources.
- Ability to assess FAIRness of existing data, and to capture, process, analyse, and preserve data according to OS principles.
- Experience in using tools for conducting research, managing and sharing research output.
- Commitment to undertaking training on digital-oriented research practices.
- Research management skills: Ability to design an open research strategy, implement an open research vision, and coordinate research activities that embed open science principles.
- Entrepreneurial skills: Ability to identify and apply for OS funding opportunities; ability to acquire funding that furthers open science goals, writing grants and funding applications.
- Good understanding of legal aspects of research relevant to their field of expertise, and of relevant Open Science practices. These include, but not limited to: Intellectual Property Rights e.g. copyright, patents, and trade secrets; and other Non-Personal Data e.g. use of IoT data and research data; Personal Data Protection and Governance e.g. processing Personal Data under the current legal framework, and following existing policies on Data Protection, Privacy, (Open) Licensing rules and frameworks.
- Good understanding of ethical principles e.g. transparency, diversity, and accountability; and of best practices e.g. avoiding bias in data processing when using data-driven technologies applicable to their field of expertise. These include the general ethical principles, frameworks and codes of conduct applicable to research e.g., the RRI Framework; the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity.
- Ability to balance personal and non-personal data protection requirements with Open Science/FAIR principles.

SOFT / TRANSVERSAL SKILLS

Considered equally important by Skills4EOOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

- Cooperation and collaboration
- Ethical orientation to open science principles and their broader social goals
- Adaptable: ability to build openness into the research process, staying up to date with research processes, software, data management systems, etc
- Time management: incorporate Open Science/FAIR practices in a timely way during the research cycle
- Communication and interpersonal skills: engage with a variety of stakeholders
- Project management
- Presentation skills
- Critical thinking

BACKGROUND ASSUMPTIONS

MAIN ACTIVITIES

- Promotes and supports Open Science (OS), e.g. by joining and supporting its initiatives.
- Produces research data for management, analysis, use, reuse, and dissemination.
- Collaborates with informal and formal research groups, including training students and other early career researchers on OS.
- Interacts with the general public to enhance the impact of science and research.
- Communicates research for scholarly and societal impact.
- Publishes research openly, providing metadata, data, code publicly available.

Open Science activities are apparent in all aspects of the early career researchers work flow. In conducting research, the early career researcher participates in additional activities essential to Open Science, including the following:

- Open access publishing, which can be applied to peer-reviewed journal articles, theses, book chapters, monographs, and conference papers.
- Opens data, which involves making all data that are necessary to reproduce reported results publicly accessible and digitally shareable.
- Opens materials, which includes having all components of the research methodology.

CONTRIBUTES TO WHICH OPEN SCIENCE OUTCOMES?

- By adopting the Open Science (OS) approach in their work, the early career researcher ensures that their research is carried out with a high degree of transparency, collegiality, and research integrity.
- By adopting OS approaches and practices, research input and outputs are shared.
- FAIR principles and methods are adopted and practiced.
- Scientific information is used more efficiently.
- The dissemination of knowledge is improved.
- Reproducibility of scientific findings is improved.

Further information

OPEN SCIENCE SKILLS TERMS

OS skills terms match the essential skills in this MVS to competence definitions from relevant taxonomies. The selected terms offer further information to help identify the learning objectives for skills development. Sources: European Skills, Competences and Occupations ontology (ESCO), [ResearchComp](#), [terms4FAIRskills](#), [Center Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement](#).

ESCO Research Skills: [Manage open publications](#); [Operate open source software](#); [Demonstrate disciplinary expertise](#); [Manage findable accessible interoperable and reusable data](#); [Manage research data](#); [Draft scientific or academic papers and technical documentation](#); [Perform scientific research](#); [Apply for research funding](#); [Manage intellectual property rights](#); [Apply research ethics and scientific integrity principles in research activities](#); [Perform project management](#); [Communicate with a non-scientific audience](#).

ESCO Transversal Skills: [Think critically](#); [Demonstrate willingness to learn](#); [Manage financial and material resources](#); [Show entrepreneurial spirit](#); [Comply with regulation](#); [Respect confidentiality obligations](#); [Build networks](#); [Use communication and collaboration software](#); [Demonstrate intercultural competence](#); [Work in teams](#); [Demonstrate trustworthiness](#); [Show determination](#); [Adapt to change](#); [Accept criticism and guidance](#); [Demonstrate curiosity](#); [Think innovately](#); [Keep an open mind](#); [Manage time](#); [Address an audience](#); [Plan](#); [Lead others](#); [Meet commitments](#); [Organise information, objects and resources](#); [Build team spirit](#); [Show initiative](#).

ResearchComp: [Disciplinary expertise](#); [Analytical thinking](#); [Manage personal professional development](#); [Strategic thinking](#); [Systemic thinking](#); [Write research documents](#); [Develop networks](#); [Interact professionally](#); [Communicate to the broad public](#); [Disseminate results to the research community](#).

Terms4FAIRskills: [Data policy](#); [Data costs management](#); [Data sharing and publication](#); [Assessment on FAIR data criteria](#); [Domain knowledge to contextualise data handling](#); [Research integrity process design](#); [Data processing](#); [Data curation](#); [Data costs management](#); [Crediting research contributors](#); [Data processing](#); [Open peer review](#); [Persistent identifiers management](#); [Data access risk assessment and mitigation](#); [Ethical application of patents, licenses](#); [Research governance](#).

CSCCE: [Strategy development](#); [Content planning](#); [Operational planning and implementation](#); [Engagement](#); [Project/programme design](#); [Collaboration](#); [Consultation and listening](#); [Speaking and presenting](#).

REFERENCE SOURCES

Berti, Johann, Marin Dacos, Gabriel Gallezot, Madeleine Géroutet, Sabrina Granger, Joanna Janik, Claire Josserand, Jean-François Lut, Christine Okret-Manville, Sébastien Perrin, Noël Thiboud (2022), *Passport For Open Science: A Practical Guide for PhD students*. <https://www.ouvrirlascience.fr/passport-for-open-science-a-practical-guide-for-phd-students/>

Demchenko, Y., Belloum, A., Wiktorski, T. (2017), *EDISON Data Science Framework: Part 4. Data Science Professional Profiles (DSPP)*. Release 2. https://edison-project.eu/sites/edison-project.eu/files/attached_files/node-486/edison-dspp-release2-v04.pdf

Demchenko, Y., Belloum, A., Manieri, A., Wiktorski, T., Los, W. (2016), *EDISON Data Science Framework: Part 1. Data Science Competence Framework (CF-DS)* Release 2. https://edison-project.eu/sites/edison-project.eu/files/filefield_paths/edison_cf-ds-release1-v07.pdf

European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (2021), *Digital skills for FAIR and Open Science : report from the EOSC Executive Board Skills and Training Working Group*, Manola, N. (editor), Lazzeri, E. (editor), Barker, M. (editor), Kuchma, I. (editor), Gaillard, V. (editor), Stoy, L. (editor), Publications Office, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/59065>

European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation/O'Carroll, C., Hyllseth, B., Berg, R., et al. (2017), *Providing researchers with the skills and competencies they need to practise Open Science*, Publications Office, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/121253>

Gatto, Laurence (2017), *An early career researcher's view on modern and open scholarship*, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.995702>

Janíčko, M., Zdeňka Š., McGrath, D. (2022), *Skills of PhD Graduates for Open Science and Open Innovation*. Lifelong Learning - celoživotní vzdělávání, 12 (2): 119-146. <https://doi.org/10.11118/lifele20221202139>

LERU (2018), *Open Science and its Role in Universities: A Roadmap for Cultural Change*, Advice Paper no. 24, <https://www.leru.org/files/LERU-AP24-Open-Science-full-paper.pdf>

Universities Norway (2021), *NOR-CAM – A toolbox for recognition and rewards in academic careers*. Retrieved from: <https://www.uhr.no/en/news-from-uhr/nor-cam-a-toolbox-for-recognition-and-rewards-in-academic-careers.5780.aspx>

Whyte, A., Vries, D, Thorat R., Kuehn, E., Sipos, G., Cavalli, V., Kalaitzi, V., Ashley, K. (2018), *Deliverable D7.3: Skills and Capability Framework*. EOSCPilot. <https://www.eoscpilot.eu/content/d73-skills-and-capability-framework>

Whyte, A. & Ashley, K. (2017), *Deliverable D7.1: Skills landscape analysis and competence model*. EOSCPilot. Annex A. <https://www.eoscpilot.eu/sites/default/files/eoscpilot-d7.3.pdf>

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